

5G-enabled Defence-in-Depth for Multi-domain Operations

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Abstract—In many civil and military use cases, 5G can be a segment of a more complex end-to-end solution. In such a configuration, properly using the 5G security mechanisms to achieve defence-in-depth and compliance with zero-trust architecture is challenging. In our paper, we discuss the existing 5G security mechanisms related to the connection of trusted and untrusted non-3GPP access networks (wireless and wired), 5G roaming, and the 3GPP approach to support Uncrewed Aerial Services, which provides authentication between the mobile terminal and an external server. The identified use cases show the need and opportunities for reusing 5G security mechanisms beyond the 5G network domain. We discuss the options for end-to-end defence-in-depth security provisioning in multi-domain networks, and we present two approaches to providing end-to-end defence-in-depth mechanisms. The first relies on the alignment of security policies in multiple domains and is based on security proxies. The second is based on the multi-domain network slices.

Index Terms—5G security, end-to-end security, network slicing, network virtualization, 6G security

I. INTRODUCTION

The Fifth Generation Mobile Networks (5G) have been deployed worldwide since 2020. This is the first generation of mobile networks that uses the *security by design* paradigm. The 5G security architecture can be seen as an evolution of the security architecture of previous generations of mobile networks. There is no doubt that the 5G security architecture and mechanism have been designed according to state of the art; however, there is a security problem related to the efficient implementation of security and defence-in-depth in a solution composed of multiple domains, of which one is 5G. There are many cases when end-to-end security is needed, including military ones. Mission-critical solutions may need end-to-security in a solution that is dynamically composed of multiple domains.

The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) has defined a 5G interconnection use case for Uncrewed Aerial Systems (UAS) [23], presented in Section III-C, which is interesting from the military and the Civil-Military Cooperation (CIMIC) perspectives. The use case defines an extension of 5G security mechanisms beyond 5G Core (5GC) and assumes that the UAS-Network Function (NF), part of 5GC Control Plane (CP), supports, among others, Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

(UAV) identification, authentication, authorization, tracking, and pairing between a UAV and a UAV Controller (UAVC). This use case shows the advantage of leveraging 5G security mechanisms for end-to-end security and defence-in-depth. Unfortunately, as we discuss in Section IV the 5GC not only lacks security enablers that can be used for this use case, but also the proposed 3GPP approach is not generic and does not apply to other possible multi-domain use cases. Our paper proposes two high-level solutions to address this problem.

In Section II, we briefly describe the 5G security architecture, further focusing on the 5G interconnection security in Section III. On that basis, two End-to-End (E2E) security ideas for achieving multi-domain security and more homogeneous defence-in-depth, supporting networks with the 5G and non-5G components, are described in Section V. Our conclusion and recommendations are presented in Section VI.

II. OVERVIEW OF THE 5G SECURITY ARCHITECTURE

The 5G network has been designed not only to be a *connectivity pipe* but also to have enablers that third parties can exploit for their services. Network architecture [1] separates the User Plane (UP) functions from the CP functions, uses Service-Based Architecture (SBA), network virtualization, and allows for the creation of 5G network slices. The 5GC uses the IP-based protocol stack, allowing interoperability with many Internet services and technologies, which is essential in the context of our work. All 5G internal operations and external interfaces are designed to provide appropriate security. Internal and external 5GC security is, among others, supported by the Authentication Server Function (AUSF), which handles authentication requests for 3GPP access and non-Single Network Slice Selection Assistance Information (S-NSSAI) access; the Authentication credential Repository and Processing Function (ARPF) that is part of Unified Data Management (UDM) responsible for generating the 5G Home Environment Authentication Vectors (5G HE AV); the Subscriber Identity De-concealing Function (SIDF) that is part of UDM and provides privacy protection (it is responsible for decrypting Subscription Concealed Identifier (SUCI) to reveal subscriber Subscription Permanent Identifier (SUPI)). More security-related functions for 5G interconnection are described in Section 3. The 5GC and 5G Radio Access Network (RAN) use encryption and integrity protection algorithms for the Access-

Contact author: slawomir.kuklinski@pw.edu.pl. This work has been supported by the EU H2020 project MonB5G (No. 871780) and Warsaw University of Technology IDUB-VMC (No. 45.010301) grants.

Stratum (AS) and Non-Access-Stratum (NAS) protection. The keys used for UP, NAS, and AS protection depend on the algorithm with which they are used. User Equipment (UE) uses Long term Evolution (LTE)-based [6] encryption and integrity protection between the UE and the Next Generation Node B (gNB)/Evolved Node B (eNB), i.e., radio link. The trust model for roaming and non-roaming scenarios assumes the decreasing trust the further an entity is located from AUSF (UDM, ARPF) of the Home PLMN (H-PLMN).

SBA uses a message bus for communication between the so-called NFs. NFs can be added or removed using the Network Repository Function (NRF). NRF supports confidentiality, integrity, replay protection and hides the topology of NF administrative/trust domain. It may also provide authentication and authorization to NFs based on the OAuth 2.0 framework [21]. NFs support client and server certificates and Transport Layer Security (TLS), which are used for transport protection, whilst Network Domain Security (NDS)/IPSec can be used for network layer protection. Service Communication Proxy (SCP) provides mediations-based indirect communication between NFs. Network Exposure Function (NEF) allows secure interconnection of user/operator-defined functions called Application Functions (AFs). The AFs can access 5GC exposed services and capabilities. The interface between the NEF and the AFs provides integrity, protection against replay attacks, and confidentiality.

5G enables network slices - isolated virtual networks that can be dynamically deployed (orchestrated) in order to support different services. Slices are based on templates, and the creation, modification, and termination of a Network Slice Instance (NSI) is part of the Management Services provided by the 5G Operations Support System/Business Support System (OSS/BSS) [11]. Consumers access management services through the standardized service interfaces defined in [20]. The typical service consumers for the above NSI provisioning are operators and vertical industries, respectively, as described in [19]. The slice instance management services are securely protected through mutual authentication and authorization. The Network Slice-Specific Authentication and Authorization (NSSAA) procedure uses a unique identifier of the network slice instance and the S-NSSAI, User ID and credentials that are different from the S-NSSAI subscription credentials (e.g. SUPI and credentials used for Public Land Mobile Network (PLMN) access). NSSAA takes place after the primary authentication and requires the usage of an Authentication, Authorization and Accounting Server (AAA-S), which can be hosted by either a H-PLMN operator or a third party. Management and Orchestration (MANO) security [11] is addressed by the MANO security framework [12]. The security threats to the network slices are listed in [13]. The S-NSSAI concept allows for the orchestration of slices, but only within the 5G Segment (5GS), which is a severe limitation when the 5GS is used as one of many network segments of an E2E solution. The integration of edge computing with 5G is of high practical importance, and several mechanisms supporting such integration, such as traffic redirection, have already been defined.

Furthermore, the Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) has already been integrated with 4G. This integration is complex and, in a sense, internal to the mobile network; therefore, its detailed description is beyond the scope of this paper.

III. 5G INTERCONNECTION SECURITY MECHANISMS

The 3GPP specifications are mainly focused on the security of the mobile network. However, some mechanisms support roaming security, the security of the so-called non-3GPP access, and the protection of externally exposed NFs. Recently, 3GPP has addressed security aspects of UAV communication with their Ground Control Station, which is outside the 5G domain. All of the above cases are relevant to the main topic of the paper.

Fig. 1. 5GS roaming architecture: Option A (LBO), Option B (Home Routed)

A. 5G roaming security

For secure interconnection of two or more 5G PLMNs, two entities have been introduced in 5G: Security Edge Protection Proxy (SEPP) for CP and Inter-PLMN UP Security (IPUPS) for CP. The SEPP is a non-transparent proxy that protects 5GC CP messages, providing authentication, integrity, and confidentiality of HTTP/2 transmission at the perimeter of PLMN and hiding internal PLMN topology. SEPPs are installed in both H-PLMN (H-SEPP) and Visited PLMN (V-PLMN) (V-SEPP), [1] (see Fig. 1), and are interconnected using a static Virtual Private Network (VPN) based on Internet Protocol (IP) Security (IPsec) or TLS. The user identity, service profile, and credentials of the roaming users are exchanged using the N32 interface. This interface has a CP part (N32-c) and a forwarding part (N32-f). N32-c performs the initial handshake and negotiates the parameters for message forwarding using N32-f. N32-f can provide Application Level Security (ALS) [4] if negotiated using N32-c. As shown in Fig. 1, the N32-f interface is used to transfer information between NRF, Policy Control Function (PCF) (Quality of Service (QoS)), AUSF (authentication), Short Message Service (SMS) Function (SMSF)

(SMS exchange), and UDM (user credentials, service profiles) of H-PLMN and CP entities of V-PLMN.

There are two roaming options for CP. The first, LBO, enables direct connection to the Data Network (DN) of V-PLMN. In contrast, the second, Home Routed (HR), provides connectivity between the V-PLMN and the User Plane Function (UPF) of H-PLMN connected to DN that is local to H-PLMN. The second option (Option B in Fig. 1) involves interactions between SMFs of both PLMNs and, from Release 16 [4], the IPUPSs. The role of IPUPSs is to protect UP messages by enforcing General Packet Radio Service (GPRS) Tunneling Protocol User Plane (GTP-U) security at the N9 interface. IPUPS can be implemented as part of UPF or as an independent entity [1]. Further details of the IPUPS functionality are specified in [4].

In the case of network slicing roaming, the same S-NSSAI can be used in V-PLMN as in H-PLMN, and the Network Slicing Selection Function (NSSF) of the V-PLMN determines the allowed Network Slice Selection Assistance Information (NSSAI) without interacting with the H-PLMN.

B. Security for non-3GPP access to 5GC

Non-3GPP Access Networks are IP access networks that use access technology not specified by 3GPP. In a non-roaming case, the H-PLMN's operator classifies a non-3GPP IP access network as trusted or untrusted. In a roaming scenario, the H-PLMN UDM decides whether a non-3GPP IP access network is trusted or untrusted based on the identities of the access and visited networks. For that, the V-PLMN's policy and capability of the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) or roaming agreement can be used. Please note that 3GPP and non-3GPP access can be combined.

Fig. 2. Different option of connection of non-3GPP access networks to 5GC (simplified)

The trusted and untrusted non-3GPP access is supported by several dedicated entities of 5GS [1], [22]. In all cases, the 5GC N2 and N3 interfaces are used, as shown in Fig. 2:

- Non-3GPP Interworking Function (N3IWF) is an entity that handles untrusted non-3GPP access, e.g. Wi-Fi terminals. It interacts with UPF, AMF, and AUSF. Security is achieved using Internet Key Exchange Version 2 (IKEv2), as defined in [16], to configure one or more IPsec Encapsulating Security Payloads (ESPs) [17]. The role of the IKEv2 initiator plays the UE, and the role of the IKEv2 responder takes N3IWF.
- Trusted Non-3GPP Gateway Function (TNGF) is used to connect trusted non-3GPP to 5GC and is part of the Trusted Non-3GPP Access Network (TNAN).
- Wireline 5G Access Network (W-5GAN) allows for several connectivity options. 5G-Residential Gateway (5G-RG) acts as a 5G UE and can be connected by Next Generation RAN (NG-RAN) and Wireline Access Gateway Function (W-AGF). The Fixed Network Residential Gateway (FN-RG) option is used to connect devices that do not have a 5G radio interface. The W-AGF provides the N1 interface in such a case.
- Trusted Wireless Local Area Network (LAN) (WLAN) Interworking Function (TWIF) enables Non-5G Capable over WLAN (N5CW) devices to access 5GC through Trusted WLAN Access Networks (TWAN) through Trusted WLAN Access Point (TWAP).

All connectivity options allow the connection of 5G terminals and terminals without 5G interfaces, e.g., FN-RG and N5CW. It should be noted that 3GPP has not defined the Y1, Y4, Y5 and Yt interfaces, depicted in Fig. 2, and there are no such plans.

C. UAS interconnection use case

The 3GPP has addressed the security of trusted or untrusted wireless and wired non-3GPP access networks connected to 5G. However, this concept lacks some details and has not yet been implemented. The UAS interconnection use case [23], presented in Fig. 3, is an excellent example of how authentication can be extended beyond 5GS borders, allowing authenticated pairing between the terminal (UE) and external to the 5G service platform (USS). The solution uses the 5GC SBA capabilities to add a dedicated NF to CP that may interact using the message bus with other components of CP. The case, however, is not generic: the proposed solution is not an enabler but just a specific network component. The use case defines an extension of 5G security mechanisms beyond 5GC and assumes that UAS Service Supplier (USS) is connected to 5GC using the N6 interface, i.e., the external data network interface. To support the UAS security requirements, the AMF and SMF NFs have been modified, and additional protocol primitives have been added.

IV. 5GS AS A PART OF AN END-TO-END DEFENCE-IN-DEPTH

The mobile networks, including 5G, are connected to the Internet, public clouds, private clouds, or external service platforms. Therefore, 5G can be part of a more complex network composed of different technological or administrative

Fig. 3. 5G support for UAS

domains. In the simplest case, the 5G network user can be connected by an external transport network to a service server (or cloud). Several transport segments, including Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN), can be used in more complex cases. Each transport segment, cloud, or service platform may have dedicated security solutions.

The 5G interconnection to external networks that uses the N6 (UPF) interface (Fig. 1) is technically relatively simple since 5G relies mainly on Internet protocols for data transport. However, the N6 interface hides all internal 5GC mechanisms, including security ones. For example, no information about user authentication or localization can be transferred over N6. Within a 5G network, multiple UPFs typically allow for data transfer to different networks or service providers, and each network slice typically has a UPF.

There are two common approaches to providing end-to-end security.

Firstly, the end-to-end interconnection can be set up without security mechanisms, assuming that the application will provide security. This approach is already part of the 5GS security architecture. In this case, the security mechanisms must be deployed in end-points (e.g., servers and terminals) and no defence-in-depth is provided in the case the application layer is compromised. Although, the security mechanisms can be customized for each application, or sometimes even for a part of an application, the application-level security mechanisms are unaware of the security mechanisms used in the lower layers of the system. This inability for cross-layer configuration may increase the demand for the processing power of the UE, energy consumption, and transmission overhead, potentially reducing the transmission speed.

Secondly, the application security mechanisms can be accompanied by lower-level defence-in-depth mechanisms, using which the interconnection of secure, trusted domains can be made to provide application-independent security. In this case, additional independent security mechanisms are provided in each segment of the end-to-end solution. This approach is typical in a federated multi-domain environment, such as Protected Core Network, in which each domain implements its own security policies. The problem with the approach is the

possible overhead of security adaptation at the interconnection points (security proxies); moreover, the end-to-end security and defence-in-depth is usually not homogeneous.

A way to provide homogeneous E2E defence-in-depth is the interconnection of the management plane of all domains to align security policies and reuse some mechanisms offered by one domain (cf. authentication) in the E2E defence-in-depth solution. Such a solution requires exposure of security capabilities to other domains and the ability to orchestrate these mechanisms according to the overall policy. In Section II we have identified 5G network mechanisms that can be exposed externally for multi-domain security. Although the concept of CP proxy, i.e., SEPP and IPUPS, can be used for roaming, it requires significant modifications to be used for 5GC connection with other solutions than PLMN.

The combination of inter-domain proxies, the programmability of 5G CP, and the interaction of the management systems of all domains involved in the end-to-end chain can provide a harmonized end-to-end security and defence-in-depth. A benefit of this solution would be a secure and coordinated interconnection of several domains, passing the encrypted traffic without relying on application-level security only. The following subsections present two approaches to implementing such a solution.

V. E2E SECURITY ORCHESTRATION

The first and simplest security harmonization solution is to use an E2E-Security Orchestrator (SO), called ALS-SO, and security proxies, called Universal Security Proxys (USPs). The ALS-SO, which has to be a trusted element, interacts with USPs to align security policies between domains, playing a role similar to an E-Node in a Protected Core Network (see Fig. 3). The USP is installed on each inter-domain interface and is internally composed of USP-CP and USP-DP functions. The USPs of neighbouring domains are interconnected via ALS-SO. For interactions between USPs and ALS-SO, three Security Configuration Interfaces (SCI) have been proposed. SCI allows for dynamic configuration of security parameters and mechanisms that comply with standardized cybersecurity controls, such as those defined in [31]. This defence-in-depth proposition follows the basic assumptions of the Zero Trust Architecture [32], [33] and could be considered as its practical implementation. The SCI interface would enable the configuration and control of security functions and leverages SC-SO domain security capabilities related to data flow (cf. confidentiality and integrity protection), users, and systems (cf. authentication). The interaction between ALS-SO is carried out using the SCI-m protocol, USP-CP interacts mutually using SCI-c, and USP-DP interacts using the SCI-f part of SCI. The SCI-c interface allows for the exchange of security information related to authentication, etc. The SCI-f interface transmits user data while protecting their confidentiality, integrity, and availability. The SCI-m interface is used to mediate and align security policies between domains. OSS/BSS of each domain manages 'its' USPs using a classical management interface (not specified in the paper) and integrates the USP

with security mechanisms and services provided by OSS/BSS. Fig.3 shows an exemplary implementation of USP for 5G. Following the UAS use case, we propose to implement USP-CP as AFs (USP-NF), connected to the 5G CP message bus. The function can interact with other NFs, including AUSF and UDM, via NEF. We propose to integrate the CP part of USP with UPF, similarly as it is done with IPUPS during roaming,

Fig. 4. End-to-end security configuration (a) and orchestration (b)

The first novel feature of the USP that we propose, is a declarative mechanism for data security policies, which could be based on matching of the network flow parameters with the criticality level of a specific mission, e.g., from the range of 1 (*low*)–2 (*normal*)–3 (*high*). For each criticality level, the appropriate security controls can be defined, accompanied by the specific enforcement options:

- extended access control model with the new capabilities, such as role-based and attribute-based access control [28], [34]. It extends the current 5G security model, which is based on the classic Authentication, Authorization and Accounting (AAA) approach with the Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP) security protocol [26];
- data and flow control mechanism, by introducing a software-defined firewall with secure routing and switching capabilities at the N6 interface. This mechanism was previously not considered a 5G security requirement;
- data confidentiality and integrity complying with the current state-of-the-art in cryptography [27]. Some of the existing cryptographic mechanisms in 5G can be considered outdated, e.g., use of AES-128 in CTR mode for encryption or RSA 1024-bit keys for public key cryptography. Furthermore, for military communication applications, it is required to implement specific advanced cryptographic schemes within hardware modules in addition to security capabilities implemented in the application layer;
- logging and monitoring solutions with cyber threat detection capabilities. 5G supports anomaly detection, but its scope is narrow. We propose to extend this monitoring capability to all interfaces, such as N6. More sophisticated security policy enforcement could be implemented

using open APIs for command and control, e.g., following the OpenC2 concept [24]. This could allow more critical communication only if monitoring and logging cover the required system layers, for example, the cloud, cluster, and container layers of the 4C model [25]. On the contrary, non-critical communication could be permitted with cloud layer monitoring only.

To use ALS-SO, each domain should be capable of configuring security mechanisms. Unfortunately, no protocol has yet been defined for such SCI interactions. The promising approach is to leverage the Network Configuration protocol (NETCONF [30]) as a modern solution for dynamic and software-defined network management and orchestration. The attractive feature of NETCONF is the use of the YANG object model, which is fully extensible with custom adaptations. One of the example applications of NETCONF for a security mechanism configuration is IPsec operations based on NETCONF proposed in RFC 9061 [29]. We propose to structure the configuration options of the security controls with the YANG object model and utilize the NETCONF protocol for advertising capabilities, negotiations, and security configuration of network elements.

A. ALS security provided by network slicing

Another solution, providing a uniform defence-in-depth with avoidance of transcoding of security mechanisms, is the multi-domain network slicing. However, such network slicing is troublesome. Whereas 5G supports network slicing, it does not support multi-domain slicing, even though the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) Network Function Virtualization (NFV) has partly addressed the multi-domain slicing. The ETSI approach applies hierarchical orchestration and uses a single E2E orchestrator instead of multiple single-domain orchestrators. Unfortunately, the interfaces between the domain-level orchestrators and the Master Orchestrator have not been defined. Also, neither ETSI NFV nor 3GPP define an interface that allows sending slice lifecycle requests by verticals or end-users.

Fig. 5. End-to-end security configuration (a) and orchestration (b)

Hierarchical orchestration typically requires the composition of the end-to-end slice template based on multiple, domain-specific slice templates. The composition of slice templates allows for the inclusion of different NFs and protocols. A generic Inter-Domain Network Slice (IDNS) allows the programmability of a slice security functions during the slice runtime. 5GC allows for adding UPFs, SMFs and the AFs to a slice. From the 5GC point of view can be seen as an internal 5G slice except for federating its management, e.g., using the slice management delegation mechanism defined in [19].

The extension of the 5GC slice to other domains increases the attack surface; however, at the same time, it allows the use of a 5G network security mechanism up to the service provider's premises or the cloud where the service platform is implemented. It seems necessary to install some proxies on the edge of 5 GC but allow propagation of some information from 5GC till slice 'end'. An essential value of network slicing is dynamically deploying network slices when needed. Moreover, the IDNS template may include security-related functions (firewalls, DPIs, IDS/IPS, anomaly detection engines) deployed dynamically during slice lifetime. The flexibility of the approach is very high, in contrast to the previous case.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have presented the 5GS security mechanisms, bearing in mind that 5GS can be a segment of a more complex end-to-end solution that need to provide an appropriate defence-in-depth and compliance with zero-trust architecture. To this end, we have discussed the 5GS security mechanisms related to the connection between trusted and untrusted non-3GPP access networks and 5G roaming. We also have discussed the UAS use case, which requires authentication between the mobile terminal and an external server and cooperation between multiple security domains. Finally, we have discussed options for end-to-end security and defence-in-depth provisioning in a multi-domain environment. Currently, the simplest solution is application-level security that does not require interaction with the underlying infrastructure. This is a big plus of the approach; on the other hand, the lack of interaction with the lower layers makes it impossible to reuse the security mechanisms of those layers. The alignment of security policies in different domains, the first concept proposed by us, lacks a widely accepted protocol for uniform configuration of inter-domain security proxies. It also requires the definition of generic security primitives to be configured. In fact, it needs *de jure* or *de facto* standards. The second solution to provide end-to-end uniform security is based on multi-domain network slices. This solution is very flexible and requires no definition of additional protocols, but requires a multi-domain network slice orchestrator. Unfortunately, such orchestrators have not been defined so far, despite their relatively simple architecture and functions. This is the main obstacle to this approach, which seems to be the most promising in the near future.

In further work, we will focus on the definition of generic security functions of the inter-domain slice and on the security enablers that should be exposed by 5G/6G to interconnected

domains. We plan to conduct experiments to demonstrate the viability and performance of the proposed schemes within some of the ongoing multinational research and development activities in which we participate, as such work requires significant efforts related to the modification of 5G security mechanisms.

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